

NEANIAS
**Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere,
Underwater and Space Challenges**

Deliverable

**Deliverable: D2.3 Underwater Thematic Services Release #1
(U1/U2/U3) software**

31/10/2020

NEANIAS is funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme via grant agreement No. 863448

D2.3 Underwater Thematic Services Release #1 (U1/U2/U3) software

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Document Info

Project Information			
Acronym	NEANIAS		
Name	Novel EOSC Services for Emerging Atmosphere, Underwater & Space Challenges		
Start Date	1 Nov 2019	End Date	31 Oct 2022
Program	H2020-EU.1.4.1.3. - Development, deployment and operation of ICT-based e-infrastructures		
Call ID	H2020-INFRAEOSC-2018-2020	Topic	H2020-INFRAEOSC-2019-1
Grant No	863448	Instrument	RIA
Document Information			
Deliverable No	D2.3		
Deliverable Title	Underwater Thematic Services Release #1 (U1/U2/U3) software		
Due Date	31-Oct-2020	Delivery Date	27/10/2020
Lead Beneficiary	NKUA		
Beneficiaries (part.)	EUNICE, TELEDYNE, AMU, CORONIS, ATHENA		
Editor(s)	P. Nomikou (NKUA)		
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Workpackage No	WP2		
Version	v1.0	Stage	Draft
Version details	Revision: 1. Last save: 2020-11-27, 16:24 Pages: 9. Characters: 6.486		
Distribution	Public	Type	Other
Keywords	Software; Release;		

D2.3 Underwater Thematic Services Release #1 (U1/U2/U3) software

Underwater Thematic Services Release #1 (U1/U2/U3) software Underwater Thematic Services Release #1 (U1/U2/U3) software

Change Record

version	Date	Change Description	Editor
1.0	2020-10-27	Document version submitted to EC	E. Nomikou (NKUA)

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Disclaimer

NEANIAS is a Research and Innovation Action funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, via grant agreement No. 863448.

NEANIAS is project that comprehensively addresses the 'Prototyping New Innovative Services' challenge set out in the 'Roadmap for EOSC' foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community's research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighboring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

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Underwater Thematic Services Release #1 (U1/U2/U3) software Underwater Thematic Services Release #1 (U1/U2/U3) software

Table of Contents

Document Info	2
Change Record	3
Disclaimer	4
Table of Contents	5
Abstract	6
1. Short deliverable report	7
1.1. Context	7
1.2. Table of Services.....	7
1.3. Further information.....	8
References	9

D2.3 Underwater Thematic Services Release #1 (U1/U2/U3) software

Underwater Thematic Services Release #1 (U1/U2/U3) software Underwater Thematic Services Release #1 (U1/U2/U3) software

Abstract

This deliverable presents the list of the thematic underwater services of WP2 released by NEANIAS project in its first release cycle, due in M12 of the project.

D2.3 Underwater Thematic Services Release #1 (U1/U2/U3) software

Underwater Thematic Services Release #1 (U1/U2/U3) software Underwater Thematic Services Release #1 (U1/U2/U3) software

1. Short deliverable report

1.1. Context

The deliverable D2.3 “Underwater Thematic Services Release #1” is produced in the context of WP2 “Underwater Research Services” of NEANIAS project. Services released are further detailed in deliverable D2.4 [2].

The deliverable refers to services released under the group of thematic services for the Space Community, namely:

- ✓ U1- Bathymetry mapping from acoustic data
- ✓ U2 - Seafloor mosaicking from optical data
- ✓ U3 - Seabed classification from multispectral, multibeam data

This document serves as a short reference to the respective digital artifacts (as the deliverable is of type “OTHER”), presenting a brief enumeration of the services delivered, located in the next subsection 1.2 “Table of Services”.

1.2. Table of Services

The following table presents the services released in this 1st cycle.

Table 1 – Services and software released

Short name	Sector ¹	Lead ²	TRL ³	Version ⁴	Core Integration ⁵	Documentation Status ⁶	Testing Status ⁷	EOSC Registration Status ⁸
UW-BAT	Underwater	TELEDYNE	TRL7	1.0.0	AAI in progress	In progress	In progress	no
UW-MOS	Underwater	CORONIS	TRL7	1.0.0	AAI	complete	In progress	no
UW-MAP	Underwater	ATHENA	TRL7	1.0.0	AAI	complete	in progress	no

¹ Thematic Service Application Domain

² Organization leading implementation

³ TRL level at release. All services start from TRL6.

⁴ Version according to service issuer

⁵ Integration level w.r.t. NEANIAS core services developed in WP6 (AAI, Accounting, Monitoring, FAIRness support ...)

⁶ Level of documentation status: draft, under-update, complete, validated

⁷ Testing status: mention the status w.r.t. unit, integration, user acceptance testing (N/A, in progress, complete, failed)

⁸ Is service listed in Neanias and EOSC catalogue? (yes, in progress, no, n/a)

D2.3 Underwater Thematic Services Release #1 (U1/U2/U3) software

Underwater Thematic Services Release #1 (U1/U2/U3) software Underwater Thematic Services Release #1 (U1/U2/U3) software

1.3. Further information

All services of the release are available under the NEANIAS development infrastructure. Depending on the service provisioning model, the services may be already available or under delivery within WP7 deployment tasks for their broader availability.

The next full release cycle is planned for M24 of the project, yet several interim releases of services will be scheduled by their respective providers and contributors.

The details about the Space services architecture and software development plan can be found in D2.1 [1].

The details about the services released can be found in D2.4 [2].

D2.3 Underwater Thematic Services Release #1 (U1/U2/U3) software

Underwater Thematic Services Release #1 (U1/U2/U3) software
Underwater Thematic Services Release #1 (U1/U2/U3) software

References

- [1] NEANIAS WP2 Collaboration, D2.1 “Underwater Research Services Report on requirements, Specifications & Software development Plan” (2020)
- [2] NEANIAS WP2 Collaboration, D2.4 “Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1” (in preparation)